

Chemotherapy Explained: A Realistic Guide for Patients and Caregivers

From Asst.Prof.Dr. Ahmet Sami Bosnak

Chapter 4: Cancer Fatigue

Everyone feels tired sometimes, but cancer patients experience fatigue at a level that is hard to explain to others. The fatigue and weakness felt during chemotherapy are unlike ordinary tiredness.

What Is Cancer Fatigue?

Cancer fatigue is a strong and persistent sense of low energy. It is the most common complaint among people undergoing cancer treatment. Its severity,

frequency, and duration vary from patient to patient. Many patients and their relatives believe it will improve with rest, but cancer-related fatigue often does not. It can severely disrupt daily life, leading to physical, emotional, social, and mental problems. Despite its impact, fatigue is one of the least discussed symptoms in hospitals. Patients often avoid telling healthcare providers because they think nothing can be done. Initially, they try to manage it on their own, but hope fades over time.

Symptoms of Cancer Fatigue

- Persistent tiredness and exhaustion, affecting physical, emotional, mental, or spiritual well-being.
- Pain in various parts of the body, especially arms and legs.
- Lack of motivation for daily activities like eating or shopping.
- Poor concentration and difficulty thinking clearly.

Causes and Contributing Factors

- The cancer itself.
- Medical problems during treatment such as fluid loss, electrolyte imbalance, fever, infections, nausea, pain, or anemia.
- Chemotherapy or radiotherapy.
- Lack of sleep.
- Depression.
- Lack of physical activity.
- Older age.

Cancer fatigue does **not** mean the cancer is progressing or that treatment is failing.

What You Should Do

Fatigue cannot be measured by a device. Communicate openly with your healthcare team. Your doctor or clinical pharmacist may ask you to rate your fatigue from 1 to 10.

Keep a **fatigue diary** to record when and how severe your fatigue is. Identifying patterns helps plan your day more effectively. Some medications may worsen fatigue. Always inform your doctor or pharmacist before starting or stopping medications.

When to Seek Urgent Medical Help

- Dizziness, loss of balance, or falls.
- Sudden worsening of fatigue.
- Sudden shortness of breath or palpitations.

Self-Care at Home

- **Track your fatigue** daily to identify your best and worst times. Plan important tasks for your good hours.
- Use a notebook or phone reminders to avoid forgetting responsibilities. Crossing completed tasks improves motivation.
- Ask for help when needed.
- Eat before you feel weak. Prefer smaller, frequent meals and healthy snacks.
- Soft or liquid foods (soup, pudding, scrambled eggs) are easier to eat.
- Stay hydrated. Unless your doctor restricts fluids, drink plenty of water.
- Make mealtimes calm and pleasant.
- Monitor your weight and report unplanned loss to your healthcare team.
- **Exercise** lightly. Inactivity worsens fatigue. Start with short walks (5–10 minutes, 2–3 times a week) and gradually increase to 20–30 minutes, 3–4 times a week. Stop if you experience shortness of breath, rapid heartbeat, or discomfort.
- **Sleep hygiene** matters. More sleep does not fix cancer fatigue. Stick to a regular schedule.
 - Sleep longest at night.
 - Avoid long naps before bedtime.
 - Take a warm shower, dim lights, listen to calm music before bed.
 - Avoid screens (phones, TVs, computers) before sleep.
 - Don't eat heavy meals before bedtime.

- Avoid smoking, alcohol, and caffeine at night.
- Your mood, beliefs, and stress responses influence how tired you feel. Emotional reactions like sadness or anger are normal.
- Don't expect to "return to normal" immediately after treatment. Give your body time to recover.
- Talk to someone you trust. Writing feelings in your diary can help.
- Accept help from family and friends. Share or delegate essential responsibilities.

Conserving Energy

- Sit down while showering, drying off, or brushing teeth. Use a bathrobe instead of a towel.
- Know your energy peaks and plan your day accordingly.
- Wear slip-on shoes.
- Sit while putting on socks or shoes.
- Arrange chairs along long hallways as resting spots.
- Slide or push objects instead of lifting.
- Ask for help with cooking and shopping. Prepare easy meals or cook larger portions to save energy.

Supporting Children While Fatigued

Cancer fatigue can make parents feel they are letting their families down. This is common but manageable.

- Explain to your child that you feel tired and may not be able to do everything as before.
- Listen to their reactions. They may offer creative solutions.
- Plan seated or low-energy activities together. Examples:
 - Balloon games.
 - Face painting with old makeup.
 - Playing in the bathtub with bubbles.
 - Dress-up games using clothes from your closet.

- Watching a movie with plain popcorn.
- Avoid lifting small children.
- Involve them in age-appropriate tasks.

For Caregivers

- Care for yourself to care for others.
- Take at least one day a week for yourself.
- Watch for signs of stress such as irritability, appetite loss, or sleep problems.
- Talk about your emotions with family or friends.
- Share responsibilities if possible.
- Educate yourself about the illness. Knowledge reduces stress and improves care quality.

This article was inspired by a patient who contacted me through this platform.

Ref: BC Cancer Fatigue/Tiredness Symptom Management Guideline.